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Fabrication Of Hybrid Manual Solar Egg Incubator In Rural Areas; A Tool For Poverty And Unemployment Reduction In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This practical project highlight the concept of hybrid manual egg incubator, concept of poverty, unemployment and causes of poverty such as global distribution of resources, over population, environmental degradation, and inadequate education. it further explain the procedures of addressing poverty through fabrication of hybrid manual egg incubator which include, increase income earning of the farmers, sources of employment, to make poultry farmer self-reliant. The challenges highlighted are discussed in the recommendations.

Keywords: hybrid manual egg incubator, poverty

INTRODUCTION

Construction of hybrid manual solar egg incubation in rural areas in Nigeria is the greatest way towards improving poultry production particularly in regions with limited access to reliable electricity (Abdulrazak 2019) there is a high demand on egg consumption due to increase in the global poplace. (Boleli et al., 2016). Chicken production for both commercial and non .commercial purposes has become a culture within both rural and urban dwellers in the recent years.

Incubation plays essential role in the poultry production, as it directly affect hatchability rates and consequently, the profitability of poultry farming. Olden days incubator, which rely on electric power, can be limited by accessibility, operational cost, and inadequate supply of electric power. (Ahmed et al., 2021) different types of egg incubator were design and fabricated by different people using different energy sources, ranging from electricity, biogas, generator of different fuel, diesel, petrol the gas or solar (Muleta, 2023)

This paper is aimed at highlighting the important of construction hybrid manual solar egg incubators in rural areas and it impact toward poverty and unemployment reduction.

Sanusi (2018) in his own view toward impact of fabrication manual solar incubator in rural areas in Nigeria observed that, the continued deterioration of the national economy is a clear signed to every Nigerian to try hard for a reliable and independent means a survived. This can only be realized through improved vocational training programmes with emphasis on functional poultry education.

Sanusi (2018) further lamented that since there is a strong link between poverty and rurality. In Nigeria over 70% of poor people live in rural areas where enrolment rates in all types of education are low, reducing poverty and unemployment rate therefore, will entails increasing rural educational opportunities. Meaning to said for effective implantation of hybrid manual solar egg incubator in the rural areas the individual or member of the community must be educated.

Conceptual Framework

Hybrid manual solar egg incubator: the Design and construction of hybrid manual solar egg incubators bring important innovation in the poultry industry, more especially in areas where electricity supply is insufficient. The combination of solar energy with manual control system not only enhance sustainability but also promote the efficiency of egg incubation. Poultry training includes egg hatching, brooding, and incubation (Alhassan 2022). The egg incubator is a device which can control the temperature and humidity in the preparation for the hatching process. By using an egg incubator, the hen does not need to incubate the egg manually. This incubator device can help farmer with the hatching of eggs to produce chicken Sanusi (2018). An incubator is a prototype temperature control of hatchery incubator using microcontroller. The nature of hatching process takes 21 days with a temperature of 9102 of or 37 to 38.9°C.

Materials needed for the construction of hybrid manual solar egg incubator

1. **Solar cell:** (Photovoltaic PV) Khatri et al., (2019) state that solar powered incubators effectively keep temperatures within optimal ranges contributing to higher hatch rates compared to traditional method. Shipa et al, (2020) solar energy is obtained from solar photovoltaic PV cells made from semiconductors; such as silicon. Usually when the light stick the cell, some of this is observed within the semi conductor materials and knocks loose electrons, allowing them to flow freely hence generating flow of electron current. When PV cells are connected in series or parallel connections, they form module and a series or parallel connection of PV modules form a PV array. The PV cells are used to absorb the suns radiation and the energy obtained in the radiation causes PV cell to produce a voltage.
2. **Incubator:** the eggs to hatch are put in the incubator, the sizes and capacity of the incubator varies depending on the types selected and the nature of the work at hand.
3. **Battery:** selection of the battery to be used depend on the capacity of the incubator and PV cell to be used.
4. **Regulator** (Control switch) are used to control the amount of current flowing from PV cell to incubator.
5. **Cable:** are used for connection the PV cell, battery and incubator

Poverty

Poverty is a condition of having insufficient resources or income. In its most extreme form poverty is lack of basic human needs such as adequate and nutritious food, clothing, housing, clean water, and health services, extreme poverty can cause terrible suffering and death, and even modest level of poverty can prevent people from realizing many of their desires. (Sanusi 2018). The world poorest people may of whom live in developing areas of African, Asia, Latin America, and Eastern Europe struggle daily for food, shelter and other necessities.

Unemployment

Unemployment is undoubtable one of the major problems facing Nigeria today. Unemployment leads to a wastage of human resources and a slow down in the rate of economic development since individuals forming a section of the labour force are not given the much needed knowledge and skills training to make meaningful contributions to the nation productivity and economic growth. A nation that can mobilize it human resources can achieve anything even with limited natural materials resources (Sanusi 2018). Unemployment is enforced idleness of wage earners who are able and willing to work but can not find jobs.

Causes of Poverty and Unemployment

Nurudeen (2019) stated that, poverty and unemployment has many causes, some of them very basic some experts suggest for instance, that the world has too many people, too few jobs and not enough food. But such basic cases are quite interactable and not easily eradicated. In most cases, the causes and effects of poverty interact, so that what makes people poor also create condition that keep them poor.

Factor that may lead to poverty includes:

- **Global distribution of resources:** many experts agree that the legacy of colonialism accounts for much of the unequal distribution of resources in the world economy. In many developing countries the problems of poverty are massive and pervasive. Because their natural resources are control by developed countries. They get inexpensive natural resources from poorer countries in African and Asia.
- **Over population:** the situation of having large number of people with few natural resources and too little space is closely associated with poverty, it can result from high population density (the state of people to land area, usually expressed as numbers of person per square kilometre or square mile) or from low amounts of resources, or from both.
- **Environmental degradation:** in many parts of the world including Nigeria environmental degradation the deterioration of the natural environment, including the atmosphere. Bodies of water, soil and forest is an important cause of poverty. Environmental problems have led to shortage of food, clear water, materials for shelter and other essential resources.
- **Inadequate education and employment:** illiteracy and lack of education are common in poor countries. Government of developing nation often cannot afford to provide for good public schools, especially in rural areas where as virtually all children in sub Saharan Africa attend elementary school without education, most people cannot find income generating work. developing countries tend to have few employment opportunities, especially for women, as a result, people may see little reason to go to school (Nurudeen, 2019).

Addressing challenges of poverty and unemployment through fabrication of hybrid manual solar incubator:

Education in whatever form is aimed at modeling a child or the individual into a better person relevant to his immediate environment. achieving poverty reduction through fabrication of hybrid manual solar incubator cannot be achieved without education (Nurudeen, 2019) it is in recognition of the above concept fabrication that technical and vocational education and training for poverty alleviation should be given utmost priority by government, having in mind the further consequences and task ahead for sustainable development in rural areas.

The future prospect and success of the fabrication of hybrid manual solar egg incubator would depend on the continuation and expansion of the existing training programmes and strengthening the existing cooperation both with national and international, as well as starting non formal training programmes for the government poverty alleviation effort towards sustain welfare of the people and development (Sanusi, 2018).

Further lamented that, in Nigeria, the need to forestall the poverty and unemployment problem become paramount and can be best achieved by training the individual to be self reliance, thereby increasing their productivity and service, which will bring about national development Igwe (2010) in his own view towards impact of fabrication hybrid manual solar egg incubator observed that every citizen should be equipped to contribute to the welfare of the country. The highest possible welfare is achieved only when each individual produces to the limit of his capacity. Therefore, every citizen should be skilled in one type of occupation or the other. The economic and social well being of any society is depend upon the quantity and quality of goods and service available to its citizen (Igwe, 2010).

Vocational agricultural education has an essential role to play in poverty and unemployment reduction. Poultry farming is one of the area that promote job creation and economic growth. (Aliyu, 2019) outlined important of constructions solar base incubator as follows:

- To provide young people with sound knowledge of basic principles and technique of poultry production
- To increase income earning of the farmers
- To make poultry farmer self reliant
- Source of employment to the youths in rural areas
- Bed rock to security
- Stimulate technological and industrial development

Challenges of Fabrication Hybrid Solar Incubator in Rural Areas

1. The material to be use in the construction of solar base incubator is not available in the rural areas
2. Lack of competent personal to train people in the rural areas
3. Lack of fund 70% of the poor people live in rural areas
4. Lack of guidance and counselling: sometime people in the rural area are not accepting innovation

CONCLUSION

Agriculture is the main way of making a living either as pure subsistence farmers or with a little semi commercial farming. Majority of the farmers in rural areas are poor people faced with many constraints that keep them poor such as lack of knowledge and skill, lack of information and knowledge about what to produce and how to produce to earn more money. The above reasons arouse the interest the researcher to design this incubator which used solar energy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The materials used for the fabrication of hybrid manual egg incubator should be made available in the rural areas.
2. Competent staff should be posted to rural areas to train the trainee in the rural area, the training should be based on real practical
3. There is need for the government to provide fund for proper takeoff of the programme.
4. There is need for continuation and expansion of the programmes in the rural areas.
5. There is need of public enlightenment to educate the people toward impact of using solar base incubator.

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